

A Study of Emotional Intelligence and Self-Concept on the Mental Health of Undergraduate Students

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Abstract: The aim of this study was to assess the Self-concept and Emotional Intelligence on the mental health dimensions of Arts and Science (undergraduate) UG students. Mangal Emotional Intelligence Inventory, Self-Concept Scale and Mental Health Inventory were administered on students with Socio-demographic sheet. Purposive sampling method was adopted to students' sample. 't' test was carried for statistical analysis and interpretation. The results clearly revealed that there is a significant difference in the dimensions of mental health between the Science and Arts emotional intelligence groups. There is a significant difference in the dimensions of mental health between the Arts and Science students of self-concept.

Keywords: Emotions, Emotional Intelligence, Personality, Self-Concept, Human behavior, Mental health, Self-awareness, Managing emotions.

1. INTRODUCTION

The word Emotional Intelligence was originally coined by Mayer, J. D. and Salovey, P. (1997) to describe qualities like understanding one's own emotions, empathy 'for feelings of others', and managing one's emotions. The sustained interest in the topic began with the publication of two important articles in 1990 by these authors. Later the concept was popularized by Goleman Daniel (1995) with the publication of his bestselling book titled 'Emotional Intelligence'.

Salovey and Mayer's original Model (1990) identified emotional intelligence as the ability to monitor one's own and other's feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them, and to use this information to guide one's thinking and action". According to Salovey and Mayer (1990), subsumes Gardner's inter and intrapersonal intelligences, and involves abilities that may be categorized into five domains: Self-awareness, managing emotions, motivating oneself, empathy & handling relationships. Goleman (1995) has adapted Salovey and Mayer (1990)'s model into a version. Goleman's model of intelligence is also a mixed model and it is characterized by the five broad areas. They are knowing one's emotions (Self-awareness), managing emotions (Self-management) motivating oneself, recognizing emotions in others (Social awareness) and handling relationships (Relationship management).

Self-concept may be defined as the totality of perceptions that each person has of themselves, and this self-identity plays an important role in the psychological functioning of everyone. By self, we generally mean the conscious reflection of one's own being or identity, as an object separate from other or from the environment. The self-concept as an organizer of behaviour is of great importance. Self-concept refers to the experience of one's own being. It includes what people come to know about themselves through experience, reflection, and feedback from others. It is an organized cognitive structure comprised of a set of attitudes, beliefs, values, variety of habits, abilities, out looks, ideas and feelings of a person. Consistency of behaviour and continuity of identity are two of the chief properties of the self-concept. Wylie (1974) and Mishra (1989) indicates that self-concept is positively related with their school achievement.

Self-concept is a factor which helps to study the human behaviour and personality. The self-concept is composed of relatively permanent self-assessments, such as personality attributes, knowledge of one's skills and abilities, one's occupation and hobbies, and awareness of one's physical attributes. For example, the statement, "I am lazy" is a self-assessment that contributes to the self-concept. In contrast, the statement "I am tired" would not normally be considered part of someone's self-concept, since being tired is a temporary state. Nevertheless, a person's self-concept may change with time, possibly going through turbulent periods of identity crisis and reassessment.

Mental health is perceived as a positive source contributing to asset development individually, socially, and economically (WHO, 2004) The World Health Organization conceptualized mental health separate from mental ill-health and defined the concept as a state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to his or her own community. On the other hand, better mental health outcomes in adolescents are characterized by greater adaptation in family, society, and school environment, improved quality of life (Hoagwood et al, 1996). The rise in mental health issues in adolescents is a growing concern in the school and for the community counsellors, and educators.

Bhatia (1982) considers mental health as the ability to balance feelings, desires, ambitions and ideals in one's daily living. It means the ability to face and accept the realities of life. Menninger (1945) writes mental health as the adjustment of human beings to the world and to each other with a maximum of effectiveness and happiness. It is the ability to maintain an even temper, an alert intelligence, socially considerate behavior and a happy disposition. well-adjusted person has some insight into and an understanding of his motives, desires, his weaknesses and strong points. He can evaluate his behaviour objectively and can accept his short-comings and weaknesses. He respects, and feels secure in the group. worth-while and important. He has self-respect and feels secure in the group.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A study by Chu (2002) revealed that males have high level of emotional intelligence than that of females. The probable reason for the present findings might be due to the fact that emotional intelligence primarily deals with managing and expressing one's emotions as well as social skills. Hunt and Evans (2004) have reported in their study on individuals (181 males and 233 females) having traumatic experiences and simultaneously studied their emotional intelligence level, and the results showed that males have higher emotional intelligence than females.

Ramesh and Thiagarajan (2005) found that the self-concept of B.Ed. trainees is high and there is no significant difference due to gender, community, locality and optional. The study also revealed that, the higher the qualification, higher is the self-concept. Hirunval (1980) conducted a study on self-concept, achievement, classroom climate and academic performance. The result of the study revealed that self-concept and academic performance were positively related.

Balaji Arumugam et al. (2013) Mental health problems among adolescents and its psychological correlates. The mental health problem psychosocial in this study was associated female sex, less age, higher socio economic status, unhealthy home environment (renes fighting, parental abuse), sibling rivalry, unhealthy school environment (fight with friends) and the type of family, single parent were not associated with the mental problems. Sanidev Verma and Pushkrit Gupta (2011) conducted a study of emotional intelligence relation to mental health and adjustment of secondary school students. The result of research revealed that correlation between emotional intelligence and mental health is significant and another correlation between emotional intelligence and adjustment proved significant. The t-ratio regarding emotional intelligence between male and male is significant but after considering adjustment the result came to just opposite negative.

3. METHODOLOGY

Objectives:

- To assess the Self-concept on mental health of Arts and Science (undergraduate) UG students.
- To study the Emotional Intelligence on mental health of Arts and Science UG students.

Hypotheses:

- There will be significant difference of self-concept on mental health of Arts and Science UG students.
- There will be significant difference of Emotional Intelligence on mental health of Arts and Science UG students.

Variables:

- **Independent variables:** Emotional intelligence and Self Concept
- **Dependent Variable:** Mental health

Sample:

In order to examine the above-mentioned hypotheses, a total sample of 120 under-graduate students from Arts (60) and Science (60) faculty were selected from Government First Grade College, Vijayapur. The age range of sample is 19 to 22. Purposive sampling method was adopted to students' sample.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. The students included were of the age group of 19 to 22.
2. UG students were included from only arts and science faculty.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. The students below the age group of 19 and above the age group of 22 were not included as the sample for study.
2. Other faculty apart from arts and science were not included.

Measures Used:

1. Mangal Emotional Intelligence Inventory (MEII):

Mangal Emotional Intelligence inventory was developed by Dr. S.K. Mangal and Mrs. Shubhra Mangal (2009) which consists of 100 items in all with response categories like yes or no. The scoring is done with the help of scoring key provided in the manual. Accordingly, the one who scores high is said to have high Emotional Intelligence and vice-vase. The reliability of scale is significant. The validity is adequate.

2. Self-Concept Scale (Saraswat, R.K., 1999):

The Self Concept Questionnaire developed by Raj Kumar Saraswat (1999) consists of 48 statements, in which there are six dimensions viz., physical, social, temperamental, educational, moral and intellectual (appendix III). Each statement is provided with five alternatives, to give their responses ranging from most acceptable (5) to least acceptable (1). The summated score of all the 48 items provide the total self-concept score of an individual.

3. Mental Health Inventory (Dr. Jagadish and Dr. Srivatsava):

This inventory is developed by Jagadish and Srivastava (1988) which is consisting of 56 items distributed along 6 dimensions of mental health, they are positive self-evaluation, perception of reality, integration of personality, autonomy, group oriented attitudes, environmental mastery. There are 24 positive and 32 negative items and the scoring is of Likert type. The inventory has four response categories namely always, often, rarely and never. A score of 4,3,2 and 1 is assigned to response category of positive statement and for negative item the scoring is reversed. Thus, one is considered as well as total. The reliability of the inventory has been found to be 0.73 and the validity is quite satisfactory (0.54).

Statistical Techniques:

- Descriptive Statistics (Mean and SD)
- 't' test was carried out to find out the significant difference between the UG students of Arts and Science faculty.

4. RESULTS**Table-1: Means, SDs and t-values of mental health in the courses of self-concept (N=120)**

Self-Concept		PSE	POR	IOP	AUT	GOA	EM	TMH
Science	Mean	32.65	32.78	32.74	26.92	30.48	32.17	187.74
	SD	3.26	2.82	3.92	3.68	4.33	3.94	21.95
Arts	Mean	29.49	29.63	29.72	25.18	27.72	27.18	168.92
	SD	3.45	2.16	4.31	3.49	4.63	3.87	21.91
‘t’ values		6.77**	6.33**	6.45**	5.91**	4.78**	6.24**	6.12**

**Significant at 0.01 level

Table-2: Means, SDs and t-values of mental health in the courses of Emotional Intelligence (N=120)

Emotional Intelligence		PSE	POR	IOP	AUT	GOA	EM	TMH
Science	Mean	32.46	30.78	33.08	29.82	30.63	28.54	185.31
	SD	3.32	2.76	4.22	3.51	4.43	3.48	21.72
Arts	Mean	30.49	25.38	30.56	24.68	26.49	29.72	167.32
	SD	3.55	2.25	3.19	3.27	4.15	3.66	20.07
‘t’ values		6.92**	6.21**	6.86**	6.12**	6.33**	6.19**	6.38**

**Significant at 0.01 level

5. DISCUSSION

Table-1 gives mean, SD and t-values of mental health of students belonging to categories of self-concept (Science and Arts). It is observed that the Science self-concept group has a mean of 187.74 in the total mental health (TMH) and that of Arts students' self-concept, it is 168.92. This reveals that self-concept of Science students has higher mean scores than the Arts students' self-concept group in total mental health (TMH). The t-value of 6.12 is significant at 0.01 level which shows that there is a significant difference in the scores of dimensions of mental health between the two samples of self-concept. Thus Science students with self-concept are found to be more mentally worthy than the self-concept students of Arts. The Self-concept is a dominant element in personality pattern, there are several terms that are virtually synonymous with self-concept among them are 'self- image', the 'ego', 'self-understanding', 'self-perception', and 'phenomenal self'.

Table-2 explains the mean SD and t-values of mental health of the sample groups belonging to Science and Arts students' emotional intelligence. The obtained results show the mean of Science students' emotional intelligence in Total Mental Health (TMH) of mental health is 185.31 and of Arts students' emotional intelligence is 167.32. The t-values of 6.38** is significant at 0.01 level. This approves that there is a significant difference in the dimension of mental health between the Science and Arts emotional intelligence groups. The Science students' emotional intelligence is found to have more mental health than the Arts students. This gives direction that Science students' emotional intelligence has higher emotional control, emotions, thoughts, abilities etc. recognizing, managing and regulating one's own mental health. This definitely indicates that emotional intelligence produces significant differences in mental health between two course students.

6. CONCLUSION

- There is a significant difference in the dimensions of mental health between the Science and Arts emotional intelligence groups.
- The Science students' emotional intelligence is found to have more mental health than the Arts students.
- There is a significant difference in the dimensions of mental health between the Arts and Science students of self-concept.
- The Self-concept of Science students has higher mental health than the Arts students' self-concept group.

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